

USING STUDENT-CENTERED LEARNING TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

All researchers emphasize the need for an individual approach to teaching students, the importance of a unified educational strategy for universities as the main condition for successful work with students. However, there are still no generalizing scientific and pedagogical works that holistically reveal the process of using the technology of student-centered learning. The social significance of student development and the analysis of the state of scientific development of this process determined the choice of the problem of this study, which is to determine how to use technologies for student-centered learning in university setting. The purpose of the article is determined by the need to identify the conditions for using the technology of student-centered learning in the conditions of a modern university.

Keywords: Availability, Self-Regulatory Behavior, Level of Abilities, Capabilities, Adaptation, Step-By-Step Nature, Awareness, Correction, Cognitive Aspects.

INTRODUCTION

A person's personal development depends on his individual characteristics. They are associated with the nature of a person's activity, peculiarities of thinking, range of interests and requests, as well as his behavior in society. That is why individual characteristics must be taken into account in the process of training and education. In addition, each age is characterized by certain developmental characteristics. It is known that the development of memory and thinking abilities most actively occurs in students. If these features are not used to the fullest during this period, then later it will be difficult to catch up. At the same time, attempts to get too ahead of ourselves, without taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the student, may not give the effect expected by the teacher.

Taking into account age and individual characteristics served as the basis for the increasingly active use of a new personality-oriented educational paradigm within the framework of teaching. The theory and practice of personality-oriented learning technology was developed by: A.V. Petrovsky, V.I. Slobodchikov, G.A. Tsukerman, I.S. Yakimanskaya and others. All teacher-researchers believe that with personality-oriented education, personality development comes to the fore.

Thus, the implementation of a person-centered approach in education is possible subject to the following conditions:

- Availability of comfortable and safe learning conditions;
- Implementation of education of self-regulatory behavior of the individual;
- Formation and development of thinking;
- Taking into account the level of abilities and capabilities of each student in the learning process;
- Adaptation of the educational process to the characteristics of student groups.

METHODS

Personality-oriented learning assumes a step-by-step nature of the learning process: from studying the student's personality through awareness and correction of the personality, and is based, fundamentally, on cognitive aspects.

Personality-oriented learning is based on the concept that a person is the totality of all his mental properties that make up his individuality. The technology of student-centered learning is based on the principle of an individual approach, which takes into account the individual characteristics of each student, which helps to promote the development of the student's personality [4].

There is an opinion that the process of intellectual changes in students comes down to a simple quantitative accumulation of features that are already inherent in the thinking of a student, to further, purely quantitative growth, to which the word "development" itself is no longer applicable. This point of view was expressed most consistently by S. Blumer in the theory of adolescence, which also states the further uniform development of intelligence during puberty [5].

In fact, the same point of view is developed by M.M. Rubinstein. He consistently considers all the changes that occur during adolescence in the field of thinking as further progress along the paths that have already been laid in the thinking of a student. In this sense, Rubinstein's views completely coincide with the views of Blumer.

The Swiss psychologist J. Piaget studied the cognitive development of students for over half a century. Piaget viewed the cognizable from two main points of view: formal and dynamic. At the same time, Piaget considered the dynamic aspect to be more important, "since only the dynamic aspect of consideration allows us to understand the nature of things." Piaget's views on cognitive development are based on the adaptation model. "People restore a state of balance, partly by changing their behavior and adapting it to changes in the environment, partly by changing those elements of the environment that they know how to control" [7].

According to Piaget's point of view, cycles of personal development precede cycles of learning. This means that learning builds on development, but does not change it. L.S. Vygotsky thought fundamentally differently. He distinguished the leading role of education in the mental

development of a student. But education can be developmental only if we focus not on completed cycles of student development, but on incipient ones. At the same time, E. Stones notes that Vygotsky's criticism of Piaget's theory is one of the manifestations of his constant interest in the role of language in human learning. Vygotsky wrote: "The determination of the level of development and its relationship to the possibilities of learning is an unshakable and basic fact from which we can safely proceed as from an undoubted point" [8].

Thus, it is necessary to distinguish at least two levels of student development, without knowledge of which it is impossible to find the correct relationship between the course of student development and the possibilities of his learning. The first level is the level of actual development of the student's mental functions, formed as a result of certain, already completed, cycles of his development. In this case, we mean the student's current level of preparation, which is characterized by what tasks he can perform independently, without the help of an adult. The second level is the level that reflects the mental potential of personality development; this is the zone of proximal development. This level is an indicator of what the student cannot do on his own, but what he can do with a little help. The zones of actual and proximal development are individual for each student, which explains the different rates of mental development [9].

The development of a student's thinking is impossible without the participation of a teacher. Consequently, one of the main goals of the educational process as a whole and each lesson separately should be considered the cognitive development of the individual. It is this goal that is one of the main ones when implementing a person-centered approach to learning.

Personally-centered learning, to a greater extent than traditional learning, corresponds to the capabilities and abilities of the student. In student, emotional vulnerability and instability of self-esteem are often observed. Similar features are more often noticeable in oral subjects: students avoid answering and do not show initiative. The use of student-centered learning technologies in such cases gives the teacher the opportunity, taking into account the individual characteristics of students, to change the form of lessons (for example, to conduct regulated discussions) in order to increase the productivity of educational activities.

As is known, when implementing a student-centered approach to teaching, it is necessary to rely on the subjective experience of the student, and also take into account the individual selectivity of the student to the forms of tasks, the type and type of material being studied. Compliance with these requirements is especially important when working with teenagers, since one of the age-related features in adolescence is the so-called sense of adulthood [10].

Implementing a student-centered approach is impossible without studying the student's personality. In this case, it is necessary to identify and take into account the psychophysiological characteristics of the student, his interests, life values, personal needs, etc. Another important factor is the assessment of knowledge. Here, not only final knowledge is assessed, but also the student's efforts. This situation is especially important for providing emotional support for adolescents with a low level of intellectual development and stimulating more productive educational activities for students with a high level of intellectual abilities [1].

RESULTS

This model of the content of education is of a design nature, since it allows one to materialize in the learning process, and ultimately “postpone” in the minds of students, scientific and cultural-value foundations, which are unshakable at any stage of human development. It is no secret that student-centered learning is an order of magnitude higher in terms of the quality of material saturation and the level of its presentation to students. The result of such educational technology is the expanded realization of the capabilities of students. Based on a qualitatively different approach, students, as a rule, can make non-standard decisions in problem situations. Currently, a different approach to understanding and organizing student-centered learning is being developed. It is based on the recognition of individuality, originality, self-esteem of each person, his development not as a “collective subject”, primarily as an individual endowed with his own unique subjective experience [8], The implementation of a personally oriented learning system requires a change in “vectors” in pedagogy: from learning as a normatively structured process (and in this sense strictly regulated), to learning as an individual activity of a student, its correction and pedagogical support.

Education does not so much set the vector of development as create all the necessary conditions for this. This significantly changes the learning function. His task is not to plan a general, unified and obligatory line of mental development for everyone, but to help each student, taking into account his existing cognitive experience, improve his individual abilities and develop as a person. In this case, the starting points of learning are not the realization of its final goals (planned results), but the disclosure of the individual cognitive capabilities of each student and the determination of the pedagogical conditions necessary to satisfy them. The development of a student’s abilities is the main task of personality-oriented pedagogy, and the “vector” of development is built not from teaching to teaching, but, on the contrary, from the student to determining the pedagogical influences that contribute to his development. The entire educational process should be aimed at this. A few thoughts on designing a learner-centered learning system. Based on its specifics, it is impossible to build an ideal model, as is customary, i.e. outline general goals and final results without taking into account the “resistance of the material”, which is the student as a bearer of subjective experience. In this sense, we distinguish between the term “projection” (mental, ideal construction of something) and design (as the creation and practical implementation of a project). The effect of creating and managing personally oriented learning depends not only on the organization, but to a large extent on the individual abilities of the student as the main subject of the educational process. This makes the design itself flexible, variable, multifactorial.

Designing a person-centered learning system involves:

- a) recognition of the student as the main subject of the learning process;
- b) determination of the design goal - the development of the student’s individual abilities;
- c) determination of means to ensure the implementation of the set goal by identifying and structuring the student’s subjective experience, its directed development in the learning process.

The implementation of personally oriented learning requires the development of educational content that includes not only scientific knowledge, but also metaknowledge, i.e. techniques and methods of cognition. It is important to develop special forms of interaction between participants in the educational process (students, teachers, parents). Special procedures are also required to monitor the nature and direction of the student's development; creating favorable conditions for the formation of his individuality; changing the prevailing ideas in our culture about the norm of a student's mental development (comparison not horizontally, but vertically, determining the dynamics of a student's development in comparison with himself, and not with another). What is needed in order to implement a model of student-centered learning in university?

It is necessary: firstly, to accept the concept of the educational process not as a combination of training and education, but as the development of individuality, the formation of abilities, where training and education organically merge; secondly, to identify the nature of the relationships between the main participants in the educational process: managers, teachers, students, parents; thirdly, to determine the criteria for the effectiveness of innovativeness of the educational process [7].

As noted above, personality-oriented learning is such learning where the student's personality, its originality, self-worth are put at the forefront, the subjective experience of each is first revealed and then coordinated with the content of education [3].

If in traditional philosophy of education socio-pedagogical models of personality development were described in the form of externally specified samples, standards of cognition (cognitive activity), then personality-oriented learning is based on the recognition of the uniqueness of the subjective experience of the student himself, as an important source of individual life activity, manifested, in particular, in cognition. Thus, it is recognized that in education there is not just a student's internalization of given pedagogical influences, but a "meeting" of given and subjective experience, a kind of "cultivation" of the latter, its enrichment, increment, transformation, which constitutes the "vector" of individual development. Recognition of the student as the main active figure in the entire educational process is personality-oriented pedagogy.

When designing the educational process, one must proceed from the recognition of two equal sources: teaching and learning [5]. The latter is not simply a derivative of the former, but is an independent, personally significant, and therefore a very effective source of personality development.

Technologization of the personally oriented educational process involves the special design of educational text, didactic material, methodological recommendations for its use, types of educational dialogue, forms of control over the student's personal development in the course of mastering knowledge. Only if there is didactic support that implements the principle of subjectivity in education, can we talk about building a student-oriented process.

Let us briefly formulate the basic requirements for the development of didactic support for a person-oriented educational process:

- educational material must ensure the identification of the content of the student's subjective experience, including the experience of his previous learning;
- the presentation of knowledge in a textbook (by the teacher) should be aimed not only at expanding its volume, structuring, integrating, generalizing the subject content, but also at constantly transforming the existing subjective experience of each student;
- during training, it is necessary to constantly coordinate the subjective experience of students with the scientific content of the given knowledge;
- active stimulation of the student to self-valuable educational activities, the content and forms of which should provide the student with the opportunity for self-education, self-development, self-expression in the course of mastering knowledge;
- design and organization of educational material, providing the student with the opportunity to choose its content, type and form when completing assignments and solving problems;
- identification and assessment of methods of educational work that the student uses independently, sustainably, and productively. The ability to choose a method should be included in the task itself. It is necessary, using the textbook (teacher), to encourage students to choose and use the most meaningful ways for them to study the educational material;
- when introducing metaknowledge about the methods of performing educational actions, it is necessary to highlight general logical and specific subject methods of educational work, taking into account their functions in personal development;
- it is necessary to ensure control and assessment not only of the result, but mainly of the learning process, those transformations that the student performs while mastering the educational material;
- the educational process must ensure the construction, implementation, reflection, evaluation of learning as a subjective activity. To do this, it is necessary to allocate teaching units, use them for organizing teaching by the teacher in the classroom, in individual work (various forms of correction, tutoring).

DISCUSSION

Let us now consider how these requirements can be implemented when designing various educational materials. The content of tasks should include a description of the methods for their implementation, which can be given directly (in the form of a statement of rules, regulations, algorithms of action), or by organizing independent searches (solve in techniques used in didactics (and the methods developed on their basis) can be divided into three groups: techniques of the first type are directly included in the content of the acquired knowledge. Ensuring their actual assimilation, they are described in the form of rules and regulations along with a presentation of the subject content of knowledge. On their basis, specific subject-specific

methods for studying educational material are developed; techniques of the second type do not follow directly from the content of knowledge on the subject. These are techniques of mental activity aimed at organizing the perception of educational material, observation, memorization, and creation of images. They constitute the main content of learning as an individual activity, since they reflect the peculiarities of the manifestation of personal characteristics that ensure cognition. On their basis, individual ways of working through educational material are formed, which, when consolidated, turn into cognitive abilities. The constant activation of these methods during learning is the main way of developing cognitive abilities, the condition for their manifestation.

The student himself is often the bearer of these methods; he can find and use them independently, on his own initiative. Didactics must identify these methods, objectify (describe) them, and offer the most rational ones in the form of techniques for assimilation by all students. Since they are based not on the subject content (as in the techniques of the first type), but on the organization of mental activity, the work on developing methods (their identification, evaluation, correction) should be carried out by a psychologist together with a didactician, and the didactic materials themselves act as psychodidactic.

The difficulty lies in the fact that the organization of mental processes, manifested in the method of educational work, does not directly follow from subject knowledge, but cannot and cannot ignore it. For example, the ability to create images (operate with them) manifests itself individually, but its manifestation is closely related to the content of objectivity. The general ability to create an image based on subject content acts as a special ability (in figurative thinking, thinking in artistic or mathematical images is highlighted). Consequently, the formation of a method largely depends on the subject content, but is not uniquely generated by it.

The source of the formation of the method is the student (his individual perceptual organization), but the method cannot be realized outside of specific subject content. This is the whole difficulty. The method cannot be derived from the subject content, but it cannot be ignored. The method cannot be specified from the outside as a technique of the first type (only through subject knowledge). To work with it, the teacher must have appropriate psychodidactic material developed by the didact together (and necessarily!) with a psychologist. A method, being basically a mental education, if it ensures the productivity of assimilation, must be recorded by the didactician, and then recommended as a rational technique.

As paradoxical as it may sound, the source of observation techniques, attention, memory, i.e. intellectual techniques, is not the teacher, but the student himself. The teacher only seems to help the student to “objectify” them. Analysis of the methods of students educational work helps to enrich didactics and creates the necessary conditions for designing the learning process (and not teaching, as something initially given).

Techniques of the second type, which are based on an analysis of how the intellect works, are implemented in learning as a process, and “disappear” in its product (a solved problem, a learned poem, a rule, a read text, etc.). Analysis of the work of the intellect (based on educational material) presupposes knowledge of what operations need to be performed in order to successfully complete the task, what their specific content should be and the sequence of execution. The teacher himself must first of all have this knowledge. Based on an analysis of his own intellectual activity, he must figure out which way can most rationally come to a solution to a problem, how to determine the general strategy for solving it, what actions need to be taken, what tasks to use, and not just demonstrate sample solutions.

CONCLUSION

After all, the teacher is also the bearer of ways to study scientific material. By exchanging his methods with students as more professionally productive, he himself can become a source of development of methods, illustrate them to students, thereby creating favorable conditions for mastering them, turning them into rational methods of mental activity. Working with methods becomes an important condition for transforming them into fixed, specially selected, consciously used methods of intellectual activity.

They are clearly not sufficiently represented in the educational and methodological literature, since their description and work with them requires special psychological training for the teacher. The source of the methods is the subject of the teaching - the student. The teacher “cultivates” them, “objectifies” them, thereby creating conditions for the development of a technology of thought. Working with the methods of student's educational work should form the basis of the organization of a personality-oriented educational process.

Individualization has recently become increasingly popular due to the desire of the modern younger generation to receive qualitatively different educational material. As is known, close interaction between a teacher and a student allows one to significantly increase the level of knowledge of the latter, and on the part of the teacher to raise one's qualification level by directly studying the individual and psychological characteristics of one's student, identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the individual and, accordingly, knowing these characteristics and specific qualities of the student, choose methods, techniques and means of pedagogical influence.

Thus, the process of “humanizing” education is based on strengthening those provisions that prioritize respect for the student's personality, the formation of independence in him, and the establishment of humane, trusting relationships between him and the teacher. The assimilation of social experience in its entirety will allow the student not only to function successfully in society, to be a good performer, but also to act independently, not just to “fit into” the social system, but to change it.

References

- 1) Pityukov V.Yu. Fundamentals of educational technology. - M., 2017, -p. 135.
- 2) Pedagogy: pedagogical theories, systems, technologies. - M., 2018. -p. 56.
- 3) Bondarevskaya E.V. Personally oriented education: experience in developing a paradigm. - Rostov-on-Don, 2017. -p.126.
- 4) Bondarevskaya E.V. Personally oriented education: experience in developing a paradigm. - Rostov-on-Don, 2017. -p.128.
- 5) E. Stones. Psychopedagogy. - Moscow, 2022. -p.95.
- 6) Ullieva S. Kh. Specific Aspects of Linguistic Study of Literary Characters. Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities. Volume 16, 2023, -p.38. <https://zienjournals.com/>
- 7) Ullieva S. Kh. Character image as an object of linguistic characteristics. International Conference on Developments in Education. Toronto, Canada. 2023. -p. 24. <https://conferencea.org>
- 8) Vafaeva Z.G., Gafurova S.T. The problem of increasing interest in the Russian language at universities. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. Volume 14, 2022. -p.59. www.geniusjournals.org
- 9) Tasheva D.S., Kubaeva N.A. Modern educational technologies in the aspect of a student-centered approach in teaching foreign languages. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. Volume 12|, 2022. - p.35. www.geniusjournals.org
- 10) Allayarova D.K., Tasheva D.S., Practical aspects of the formation of a communicative approach in the development of a linguistic personality in teaching the Russian language. Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities. Volume 18, 2023. -p.181. <https://periodica.com>